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The Dynamic Linkages of Budget Deficits and Current Account Deficits Nexus in EU Countries: Bootstrap Panel Granger Causality Test

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to test the relationship between budget deficit and current account deficit for EU-27 countries over the period 2002Q1-2013Q4 using different panel bootstrap causality test. For this analysis, we employed a method developed by Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011), which is based on the estimation of the panel model with bootstrapping critical values. We found strong empirical support for bidirectional causality between budget deficit and current account deficit for Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Spain, and UK, pointing as twin deficit hypothesis supported by Keynesian view. In addition the main results, we found that there is no relationship between budget deficit and current account deficit for 9 EU countries: Austria, France, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, and Romania, indicating support for the Ricardian Equivalence Hypothesis.

JEL Classification: C33; E62; F32; H62.

Key Words: Twin Deficits; Ricardian Equivalence Hypothesis; Cross Section Dependency; Granger Causality..

1. INTRODUCTION

The twin deficit hypothesis is one of the heavily debated topics today. The recent worldwide financial crisis and especially Eurozone crises have aggravated the discussion over the relationship between budget balance and current account balance. The co-movement of budget deficit and the current account deficit is also known as twin deficit hypothesis. There are two competing views on twin deficit hypothesis in the literature. Keynesian view, which is based on Mundell-Fleming model, asserts that the increase in the budget deficit would finally widen the current account deficit under flexible exchange rate system (Miller and Russek, 1989; Rosenweig and Tallman, 1993; Islam, 1998; Darrat, 1998; Kaufmann et al., 2002; Hatemi and Shukur, 2002; Baharumshah and Lau, 2006; Arize and Malindretos, 2008; Daly ve Siddiki, 2009). Ricardian Equivalence hypothesis (REH) negates the relationship between the budget deficit and the current account deficit. According to the REH, there is no obvious possible causal relationship between the budget deficit and the current account deficit (Barro, 1974; Buchanan, 1976; Enders and Lee, 1990; Khalid and Guan, 1999; Seater, 1993; Arize and Malindretos, 2008; Marinheiro, 2008). In addition to these views, Summers (1988) argues that the increase in the current account deficit induce the budget deficit. This reverse causality (causality runs from current account to budget deficit) is called as current account targeting hypothesis.

The early empirical studies examining the twin deficit hypothesis reached mixed results. While Latif-Zaman and DaCosta (1990), Bachman (1992), Bahmani-Oskooee (1992), Leachman and Francis (2002), Salvatore (2006), Kim and Roubini (2008) found support for the Keynesian hypothesis, Enders and Lee (1990), Dewald and Ulan (1990), Winner (1993), Kaufmann et al. (2002), Daly and Siddiki (2009) found support for the REH. Anoruo and

Ramchander (1998), Khalid and Guan (1999), Hatemi and Shukur (2002), Kim and Kim (2006), Kalou and Paleologou (2012) found support for the uni-directional causality runs from current account deficit to budget deficit. Also there is evidence for bi-directional causality that causality runs both sides. Darrat (1988), Kearney and Monadjemi (1990), Islam (1998), Arize and Malindretos (2008), Magazzino (2012) found evidence of bi-directional causality.

In the aftermath of the Eurozone crises, a number of European economies face a remarkable deterioration in their budget and current account. Especially, the sustaining of fiscal balance is related to the financial solvency of the government. So, the main purpose of satisfying fiscal balance is that a country should have a macroeconomic stability to continue the fiscal deficits within sustainable limits. These developments constitute a basis for examining the twin deficit hypothesis for EU. The aim of this paper is to identify the existence and the direction of causal relationship between budget and current account deficits in 27 EU countries for the period 2002Q1 to 2013Q4. A few studies employed panel causality analysis in order to determine the causal relationship between budget deficit and current account deficit (Rault and Afonso, 2009; Xie and Chen, 2014). However, some studies in the literature do not take account of the presence of cross correlations. Therefore, it is more useful to test cross correlation among EU countries. We employed the panel Granger causality test based on meta-analysis developed by Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011). To our knowledge, this is the first attempt to analyze twin deficit hypothesis in EU 27 countries using panel causality test.

The paper contributes to the empirical literature by investigating the budget balance and current account balance in EU 27 countries during the period 2002Q1-2013Q4. This paper is to fill the gap in the budget balance and current account balance literature as part of existing literature. Firstly, this study is to test on this causality with a panel of EU-27 during the period covering after financial crisis. Panel analysis gives more powerful results with respect to time series analysis, and so it is an important aspect for highly interdependent countries as our sample countries. Secondly, we use new panel causality approach which takes into account cross sectional dependency. Thirdly, unlike previous studies, we adopt the Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011) panel causality test based on Meta-analysis in order to avoid pre-test bias. Their methodology is a panel extension of Toda and Yamamoto (1995). The previous studies on the budget deficits and current account deficits can be seen in Table 1. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 overviews the data and describes the methodology, section 3 presents the empirical results and finally we present our conclusions and policy implications in section 4.

Table 1: Previous Empirical Literature

Author(s)	Country - Period	Method	Result(s)
Darrat (1988)	US, 1960Q1-1984Q4	Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD
Abell (1990)	US, 1979Q2-1985Q2	VAR	BD causes CAD
Enders and Lee (1990)	US, 1947Q3-1987Q1	VAR	No relationship between BD and CAD. Findings support REH.
Latif-Zaman and DaCosta (1990)	US, 1971Q1-1989Q3	Granger causality test	BD Granger causes CAD
Kearney and Monadjemi (1990)	US, UK, Australia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, 1972Q1-1987Q4	VAR	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD
Dewald and Ulan (1990)	US, 1954-1987	Linear regression analysis	No relationship between BD and CAD. Findings support REH.
Bahmani-Oskoeie (1992)	US, 1971Q1-1989Q2	Engle-Granger cointegration test	BD has a positive impact on CAD
Bachman (1992)	US, 1974Q1-1988Q4	VAR	BD causes CAD

Table 1: Previous Empirical Literature (Continued)

Author(s)	Country - Period	Method	Result(s)
Rahman and Mishra (1992)	US, 1946-1988	Engle-Granger cointegration test	No relationship between BD and CAD. Findings support REH.
Winner (1993)	Australia, 1984-1989	Linear regression analysis	BD has no significant impact on CAD. Findings support REH.
Rosenweig and Tallman (1993)	US, 1961Q1-1989Q4	VAR	BD causes trade deficits
Diboglu (1997)	US, 1960Q1-1994Q4	VAR	BD causes CAD
Islam (1998)	Brazil, 1973Q1-1991Q4	Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality between BD and trade deficit
Normandin (1999)	US, Canada, 1950Q2-1992Q3	VAR	BD causes CAD
Vamvoukas (1999)	Greece, 1948-1994	Johansen's cointegration test and Granger causality test	BD causes CAD
Anoruo and Ramchander (1998)	5 South Asian countries, 1957-1993	VAR	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD in Malaysia, CAD causes BD in other countries (Indonesia, Korea, India, Philippines)
Khalid and Guan (1999)	10 developed and developing countries, 1950-1994	Engle-Granger and Johansen cointegration test, Granger causality test	CAD causes BD only in Indonesia and Pakistan
Leachman and Francis (2002)	US, 1948Q1-1973Q4 and 1974Q1-1992Q2	Single equation procedure from Engsted et al., Granger-Lee two-step procedure and Johansen's cointegration test	BD causes CAD under a flexible exchange rate system (1974Q1-1992Q2)
Kaufmann et al. (2002)	Australia, 1976Q1-1998Q4	Johansen's cointegration test	BD has no significant impact on CAD. Findings reject the twin deficit hypothesis and, support REH.
Hatemi and Shukur (2002)	USA, 1975Q1-1998Q2	Bootstrap Granger causality test	BD Granger causes CAD for 1975-1989 sub-period, CAD Granger causes BD 1990-1998 sub-period
Fidrmuc (2003)	10 OECD countries, 1970-2001	Johansen's cointegration test and Granger causality test	Twin deficit emerged in the 1980s, but not in the 1990s
Kim and Kim (2006)	Korea, 1970-2003	Toda –Yamamoto causality test	CAD Granger causes BD
Bagnai (2006)	22 OECD countries, 1960-2005	Gregory –Hansen cointegration test with regime shift	BD is a significant determinant of the external deficit
Salvatore (2006)	G-7 countries, 1973-2005	Linear regression analysis	BD leads CAD
Papadogonas and Stournaras (2006)	EU-15 countries, 1970-2003	Johansen's cointegration test	BD has a positive impact on CAD

Table 1: Previous Empirical Literature (Continued)

Author(s)	Country - Period	Method	Result(s)
Marinheiro (2008)	Egypt, 1977-2003	Johansen's cointegration test and Granger causality test	CAD Granger causes BD
Beetsma et al. (2008)	14 EU countries, 1970-2004	Panel VAR	BD has a positive impact on CAD
Kim and Roubini (2008)	US, 1973Q1-2004Q1	VAR	BD causes CAD
Arize and Malindretos (2008)	10 African countries, 1973Q2-2005Q4	Fractional cointegration test, Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD
Grier and Ye (2009)	US, 1948Q1-2005Q1	VAR-GARCH	No relationship in the long-run and BD has a positive impact on CAD in the short-run
Daly and Siddiki (2009)	23 OECD countries, 1960-1999	Gregory-Hansen cointegration test with regime shift	Canada, Germany, Sweden, Switzerland, UK and US are in favor of the REH.
Baharumshah and Lau (2009)	7 East Asian countries, 1980Q1-2006Q4	Gregory-Hansen cointegration test with regime shift, Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD in Malaysia, BD causes CAD in Indonesia, Korea, Thailand, Philippines
Rault and Afonso (2009)	EU15, 1970-2007 EU25 1996-2007	Bootstrap panel Granger causality test	BD causes CAD in Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Italy, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland and Slovakia
Katircioglu et al. (2009)	24 small island countries, 1970-2004	Granger causality test	CAD Granger causes BD
Holmes (2010)	US, 1960Q1-2007Q4	Nonparametric test for nonlinear co-trending	Twin deficits share a common nonlinear deterministic time trend
Holmes (2011)	US, 1947-2009	Hansen-Seo threshold cointegration	The threshold cointegration approach supports the twin deficit hypothesis in the long-run. But twin deficit hypothesis would only prevail if the internal balance has reached a certain threshold (the internal balance has had to become relatively large to external balance)
Magazzino (2012)	Italy, 1970-2010	Johansen's cointegration test and Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality between BD and CAD
Kalou and Paleologou (2012)	Greece, 1960-2007	Johansen's cointegration test and Granger causality test	CAD Granger causes BD (Current account target hypothesis)

Table 1: Previous Empirical Literature (Continued)

Author(s)	Country - Period	Method	Result(s)
Trachanas and Katrakilidis (2013)	Portugal, Ireland, Italy, Greece, Spain, 1971-2009	Gregory-Hansen cointegration test with regime shift and Schorderet's asymmetric cointegration test	The asymmetric cointegration test supports the twin deficit hypothesis
Xie and Chen (2014)	11 OECD countries, 1980-2010	Panel Granger causality test	Bi-directional causality in Belgium, Finland, Greece and Iceland. BD causes CAD in Norway and Switzerland. CAD causes BD in Ireland, Spain, and Sweden. There is no causal relationship in France and UK.

Note: This table is arranged by authors using previous studies.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to test whether there is a relationship between budget and current account balance using panel Granger causality analysis by Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011) for the periods from 2002Q1 to 2013Q4. All data used in this study are obtained from the *EUROSTAT Database* for EU (European Union) 27 countries. These countries have been selected according to the data availability. We adopt panel Granger causality test based on Meta-analysis proposed by Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011). To investigate the Granger causality links between budget deficit (*BD*) and current account deficit (*CAD*), we use the level VAR model with $k_i + d \max_i$ lags in heterogeneous mixed panels:

$$BD_{it} = \alpha_{1i} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \beta_{1ij} BD_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \gamma_{1ij} CAD_{i,t-j} + \varepsilon_{1it} \quad (1)$$

$$CAD_{it} = \alpha_{2i} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \beta_{2ij} BD_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \gamma_{2ij} CAD_{i,t-j} + \varepsilon_{2it} \quad (2)$$

where $d \max_i$ is maximal order of integration order of integration suspected to occur in the system for each i and k_i is the lag orders in level VAR systems for i th country.

To test Granger causality in this system, the null hypotheses are as follows:

$$H_0 : \gamma_{1i1} = \gamma_{1i2} = \dots = \gamma_{1i,k_i} = 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

$$H_0 : \beta_{2i1} = \beta_{2i2} = \dots = \beta_{2i,k_i} = 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

Under the null (3), current account deficit (*CAD*) does not Granger cause budget deficit (*BD*) for all i . Under the null (4), *BD* does not Granger cause *CAD* for all i . Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011) use Fisher test statistic proposed by Fisher (1932) in order to test the Granger non-causality hypothesis in heterogeneous panels. Fisher (1932) considered combining several significant levels (p-values) identical but independent tests. If the test statistics are continues, p-values $p_i (i = 1, \dots, N)$ are independent uniform (0,1) variables. In this case, Fisher test statistic (λ) is written as follows:

$$\lambda = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \ln(p_i) \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (5)$$

where p_i is the p-value corresponding to the Wald statistic of the i th country. This test statistic has a chi-square distribution with $2N$ degrees of freedom. The test is valid only if N is fixed as $T \rightarrow \infty$.

However, the limit distribution of the Fisher test statistic is no longer valid in the presence of cross-section dependence among countries. As a way to deal with such inferential difficulty in panels with cross correlations, we use the bootstrap methodology to Granger causality test for cross-section dependence. Therefore,

Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011) obtain empirical distribution of the test statistic using the following bootstrap method. In simplicity, we apply on testing causality from *CAD* to *BD* in Eq. (1). A similar procedure is applied for causality from *BD* to *CAD* in Eq. (2). The steps of Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011) bootstrap procedure proceed as follows:

Step 1. In order to maximal order of integration of three variables ($d \max_i$) in the VAR system for each cross section unit, we use unit root test proposed by Dickey and Fuller (1981). We then estimate the regression (1) by OLS for each country and select the lag order k_i 's via SBC by starting $k_{\max} = 4$.

Step 2. By using k_i and $d \max_i$ from Step 1, we re-estimate Eq (1) by OLS under the null (3). Thus, we obtain the residuals for each individual.

$$\hat{\epsilon}_{1it} = BD_{it} - \hat{\alpha}_{1i} - \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \hat{\beta}_{1ij} BD_{i,t-j} - \sum_{j=k_i+1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \hat{\gamma}_{1ij} CAD_{i,t-j} \quad (6)$$

Step 3. Stine (1987) suggests that residuals have to be centered with

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_{1t} = \hat{\epsilon}_{1t} - (T - k - l - 2)^{-1} \sum_{k+l+2}^T \hat{\epsilon}_{1t} \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\epsilon}_{1t} = (\hat{\epsilon}_{11t}, \hat{\epsilon}_{12t}, \dots, \hat{\epsilon}_{12t})'$, $k = \max(k_i)$ and $l = \max(d \max_i)$. Furthermore, we develop the $[\tilde{\epsilon}_{1it}]_{N \times T}$ from these residuals. We select randomly a full column with replacement from the matrix at a time to maintain the cross covariance structure of the errors. We denote the bootstrap residuals as $\tilde{\epsilon}_{1it}^*$ where $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$.

Step 4. We generate as recursively the bootstrap sample of BD_{it}^* under the null (3).

$$BD_{it}^* = \hat{\alpha}_{1i} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \hat{\beta}_{1ij} BD_{i,t-j}^* + \sum_{j=k_i+1}^{k_i+d \max_i} \hat{\gamma}_{1ij} CAD_{i,t-j} + \tilde{\epsilon}_{1it}^* \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_{1i}$, $\hat{\beta}_{1ij}$, $\hat{\gamma}_{1ij}$ and $\hat{\delta}_{1ij}$ are obtained from Step 2 for all i and j .

Step 5. Substitute BD_{it}^* for BD_{it} , estimate (1) without imposing any parameter restrictions on it and then the individual Wald statistics are calculated to test non-causality null hypothesis separately for each country. Using these individual Wald statistics have an asymptotic chi-square distribution with k_i degrees of freedom, we compute individual p-value's. Then, the Fisher test statistic is obtained. We generate the bootstrap empirical distribution of the Fisher test statistics repeating steps 3–5 with 10.000 times and specify the bootstrap critical values by selecting the appropriate percentiles of these sampling distributions.

3. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

It is substantial to determine the cross-section dependence in panel data models because of the presence of common shocks and unobserved components. In the last few decades, we have experienced a growing economic and financial integration of countries and financial entities that indicates strong interdependencies between cross-units (Hoyos and Sarafidis, 2006). Testing the cross-section dependence, we can apply LM test statistics using the Breusch and Pagan (1980) and Pesaran (2004). The Breusch and Pagan (1980) Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test is built on the sum of squared coefficients of correlation among cross-section residuals acquired by ordinary least squares (OLS). The results from the cross-sectional dependences are shown in Table 2. These results demonstrate that the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence is rejected at 1% level of significance for budget balance and current account balance in EU countries. Hence, these empirical evidences suggest that a shock in an EU country can be transferred easily to any country in EU. This result indicates a strong evidence of cross-section dependence for our dataset.

Table 2: Cross-Section Dependence Test

Budget Balance (% of GDP)			Current Account Balance (% of GDP)		
Test	Statistic	P-value	Test	Statistic	P-value
CD_{LM1}	498.348***	0.000	CD_{LM1}	635.631***	0.000
CD_{LM2}	5.561***	0.000	CD_{LM2}	10.743***	0.000
CD_{LM}	-2.509***	0.006	CD_{LM}	-2.385***	0.009

Note: P-values is from the asymptotic normal distribution. The dataset for this test includes all sample period 2002Q1-2013Q4. *** implies statistical significance at the 1% levels.

We report the results of the causality test in Table 2 between budget balance and current account balance using a bivariate model for EU 27 countries. The results 2 propose that both null hypothesis of "BD does not Granger cause CAD" or "CAD does not Granger cause BD" cannot be rejected even at the 10% significance level for 9 EU countries, namely Austria, France, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and Romania. These results support Ricardian Equivalence Hypothesis, indicating that there is no connection between budget balance and current account balance. However, there is strong evidence to reject null hypothesis "BD does not Granger cause CAD" for Cyprus, Latvia, Malta, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Sweden at the 5% level of significance. As for Bulgaria, Finland, and Greece, there is strong evidence against the null hypothesis of "CAD does not Granger cause BD" at the 5% level of significance and for Lithuania at the 10% level. And finally, we found strong empirical support for bi-directional Granger causality between budget balance and current account balance for Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Spain, and UK. These results support that Keynesian hypothesis or Twin deficits are valid for EU countries named above.

In the Table 3, we derived Fisher test statistic value combining the p-values of countries to assess an overall hypothesis for EU27 countries. The bootstrap distribution of Fisher test statistics is derived from 10,000 replications and bootstrap critical values are received at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels based on these empirical distributions. Fisher test statistics (λ) distributes as χ^2_{2N} under the cross-section independence assumption. Therefore, the limit distribution of the Fisher test statistic is no longer valid in the presence of cross-section dependence in the mixed panels. Under the cross-section dependency in mixed panels, we can use the bootstrap method to find the empirical distributions of the Fisher test. Our results indicate that Fisher test results are higher than asymptotic chi-square critical values for both BD to CAD and CAD to BD. They are 181.987 and 138.847 significant at the one percent level for the Granger causality tests, respectively. When the bootstrap critical values are used, Fisher test shows that there is a strong empirical support for bidirectional Granger causality between budget balance and current account balance (twin deficits) at the 1% significance level for EU27 countries. These findings indicate that that the twin deficits hypothesis is supported for these countries.

4. CONCLUSION

We examined the availability of causality relationship between budget balance and current account balance over the period 2002Q1-2013Q4 for a balanced panel of EU 27 countries as part of twin deficits. We used a method developed by Emirmahmutoglu and Kose (2011), which is based on the estimation of the panel model with bootstrapping critical values. We derived some different results stemming from these empirical findings. *First*, empirical findings support the hypothesis of a causal relation from budget balance (BD) to current account balance (CAD) for some EU countries, namely Cyprus, Latvia, Malta, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Sweden at the 5% level of significance. *Second*, there is no relationship between budget balance (BD) and current account balance (CAD) even at the 10% significance level for 9 EU countries: Austria, France, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, and Romania, indicating support for the Ricardian Equivalence Hypothesis. This result supports the two deficits are not causally connected. *Third*, some findings show the inverse hypothesis of a causal relation from to current account balance (CAD) to budget balance (BD) for Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, and Lithuania. *Fourth*, we found strong empirical results for bidirectional causality between budget balance and current account balance for Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Spain, and UK, also known as Twin Deficit Hypothesis proposed by Keynesian view.

Table 3: The Results of Granger Causality Test

Budget Balance to Current Account Balance				Current Account Balance to Budget Balance			
Countries	k_i	W_i	p_i	k_i	W_i	p_i	
Austria	4	4.199	0.379	4	2.416	0.660	
Belgium	3	21.246	0.000***	3	8.259	0.041**	
Bulgaria	4	5.294	0.259	4	19.143	0.001***	
Cyprus	4	19.666	0.001***	4	4.432	0.351	
Czech Rep.	2	8.951	0.011**	2	5.97	0.051*	
Denmark	3	7.228	0.065*	3	6.985	0.072*	
Estonia	4	22.125	0.000***	4	10.584	0.032**	
Finland	4	1.908	0.753	4	12.283	0.015**	
France	4	1.729	0.785	4	7.644	0.106	
Germany	3	9.655	0.022**	3	24.939	0.000***	
Greece	4	2.256	0.689	4	15.105	0.004***	
Hungary	1	0.034	0.854	1	0.015	0.904	
Ireland	4	6.147	0.188	4	5.058	0.281	
Italy	4	25.713	0.000***	4	10.525	0.032**	
Latvia	4	10.210	0.037**	4	5.276	0.260	
Lithuania	4	5.814	0.213	4	9.423	0.051*	
Luxembourg	4	5.882	0.208	4	1.909	0.753	
Malta	4	13.317	0.009**	4	2.032	0.730	
Netherlands	4	4.920	0.296	4	3.154	0.532	
Poland	4	5.603	0.231	4	4.995	0.288	
Portugal	4	6.960	0.138	4	4.317	0.365	
Romania	4	4.329	0.363	4	0.788	0.940	
Slovakia	2	6.308	0.043**	2	0.077	0.962	
Slovenia	1	6.517	0.011**	1	1.773	0.183	
Spain	4	11.068	0.026**	4	19.762	0.001***	
Sweden	4	12.718	0.013**	4	2.337	0.674	
UK	4	18.578	0.001***	4	10.277	0.036**	

Panel Statistics							
Fisher Test Value (λ)	1%	5%	10%	Fisher Test Value (λ)	1%	5%	10%
181.987***	110.483	97.207	90.436	138.847***	109.392	96.315	90.047

Note: Lag orders (k_i) are selected by minimizing the Schwarz Bayesian criteria, W_i indicates Wald statistics and p_i shows p -value. ***, ** and * indicate the rejection of the null hypothesis at 1%, 5% and 10% significance level, respectively.

To determine the cross-sectional dependency, we start by testing whether or not there is cross-sectional dependence across the countries. So, we strongly rejected the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence at the 1% significance level. After we used the bootstrap critical values, Fisher test shows for bidirectional Granger causality between budget balance and current account balance at the 1% significance level for EU 27 countries, also as known twin deficits. The problem of budget and current account deficits likely needs a mixed policy approach which combine fiscal and monetary policy measures. Especially, after Eurozone crisis, it is very important to control the excessive imbalances in the budget and current account. We suggest that the main policy implication is essential for the EU government to reduce the public expenditures in order to sustain the balance of public finance.

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